

‘There is no America without inequality’: Imagining social justice writing in a calculus class

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Social justice mathematics pedagogies envision students “writing the world” with mathematics, in ways that often involve literal rather than metaphorical writing. However, neither the textual form nor the pedagogical processes of developing these persuasive mathematical compositions are envisioned clearly in current mathematics education research. In this poster, we present several samples of social justice mathematics writing responding to an idealized model of the COVID-19 epidemic. One was written by an undergraduate calculus student and others are “creative writing” by professors who are answering the classroom task as if they were students. Through this poster, we hope to create conversation about how students can demonstrate both mathematical knowledge and social awareness through a written text.

Overview

Social justice mathematics pedagogies envision students “writing the world” with mathematics, that is, using mathematical learning to change their communities (Freire, 2005; Gutstein, 2016; Skovsmose, 2020). Quite often, this metaphorical writing involves literal writing, for example, when a curricular lesson concludes with students writing a reflection on their work or writing a letter to a powerful stakeholder (Berry III et al., 2020). This conceptualization, however, seems to be weakly envisioned in current mathematics education research, that students will learn mathematics in relation to issues of justice, compose a written statement that unites mathematics and their critical vision in some fashion, and deploy this writing into the world to some positive effect. Even a brief consideration will generate a complex constellation of composition decisions: How much mathematical knowledge must the writing demonstrate to the teacher? Will students explain how mathematics works in public statements, or merely present the outcomes of their analysis? How does one write persuasively across the epistemological divides of

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mathematical reasoning and moral critique? How do student groups negotiate the process of producing this collective statement?

This poster aims to create conversation among researchers on what they value in social justice mathematics writing. We present several samples of social justice mathematics writing in response to a calculus activity modelling the spread of COVID-19. One sample was written by an undergraduate student in a calculus class, Ijeoma, just as the pandemic began to spread through her city of Minneapolis, Minnesota, U.S.A. The other samples are “creative writing” provided by professor co-authors, written as if they were students in a similar calculus class. We do not present the professors’ writing as ideal or perfect examples of social justice mathematics writing, but instead, as possibilities for how students might undertake the difficult task of calling attention to the appalling inequalities exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic while also demonstrating early-stage calculus knowledge. In effect, we have identified a lacuna in social justice mathematics research, and we take it as professors’ responsibility to imagine a range of possible student responses.

Layout of the poster

The poster will contain the following sections: a statement of the research problem; a brief literature review; the focal epidemiology task with the writing prompt; four brief writing samples; and a collective reflection that outlines priorities for future research on social justice mathematics writing.

An idealized COVID-19 model

The focal task is a generalized Susceptible-Infected model of an epidemic which has many unrealistic features, but is useful pedagogically for discussing calculus topics such as derivative graphs, changing slopes, concavity and inflection points. Early-stage calculus students can use Euler’s numerical method to generate graphs of monthly and of cumulative incidence of COVID-19 in an idealized community of 500 people:

Figure 1: Modeling an epidemic

The poster will contain the following sections: a statement of the research problem; a brief literature review; the focal epidemiology task with the writing prompt; four brief writing samples; and a collective reflection that outlines priorities for future research on social justice mathematics writing. The task and the teaching process will be presented more fully on the poster.

The writing prompt, modified slightly for international professors' creative writing, is:

Reflect on an issue of unfairness associated with the COVID-19 pandemic that affected any part of the world. Assume that eventually, the COVID-19 graphs in this place will look like the above graphs, except that they will have different scales on the axes and the "cumulative cases graph" will level out at a value or carrying capacity that is lower than the entire population.

Explain carefully and in detail how COVID-19 raises issues of unfairness and social justice. Use the shapes of your graphs in your answer. For example, you could try to explain where the people you are writing about would show up in the graphs, or how they would be affected if governmental policies or changing social behaviours modified the various rates of change in the graphs.

Your social justice writing should demonstrate your knowledge of calculus.

Envisioning social justice mathematics writing

In this proposal, due to space constraints, we present brief summaries and excerpts from a few of the social justice mathematics writing samples. The poster layout will present additional and longer texts. The layout will use graphic "callout" images to draw attention to writing techniques employed by each writer, particularly, demonstrating mathematical knowledge in order to criticize the dreadful impact of COVID-19 on exploited communities.

Jjeoma's real answer

There is no America without inequality [...] The coronavirus is dangerously highlighting the inequality that lower class and working-class marginalized black and brown people face. [...] When referring back to the graph above, the people who are hit by this virus before the inflection point will consist of more working-class people of color. Where we see the graph leveling out will most likely be when people in privileged places of power take this situation seriously. It's heartbreaking to know that the numbers we calculated in class translate to real-life tragedies that lower-class black and brown communities will face.

Anna's fictional answer

Anna responded to the writing prompt as if she were an international student attending university in Minnesota, whose studies corresponded with both the experience of the pandemic there and the Black Lives Matter protests against the racist police killing of George Floyd, an African American man. Her concern was that the inflection point of the graph of cumulative cases is both an optimistic target to encourage social distancing but also, that it could also become a tool of governmental control against necessary political activism.

Swati's fictional answer

Swati's answer compared the classroom graph of "new cases per month" to public daily case data from India through the lens of national policies and seasonal events. She highlighted inequalities associated with social class. The coronavirus initially reached India through the air travel of middle- and upper-class people, whose ability to social distance caused unemployment among household service providers. She reads the growth and decline stages in the real data against governmental lockdown policies, seasonal movement for agricultural distribution, and festival gatherings. She highlighted continuities across the classroom and realistic graphs, but noted the significant difference that in the real data, the "new cases per day" approaches a positive, non-zero constant, so that cumulative cases will probably continue to rise.

The poster callout graphics on the poster will us notice writers' strategies for "writing the world" through mathematical knowledge. Some of these strategies include restoring a sense of racial and class-based difference to the mathematically uniform variable of "cases," interpreting growth and decline periods in terms of public policy and cultural activities, and reading the graphs in terms of their potential for public communication or manipulation.

Collective reflection

Our collective reflection will consider dilemmas in constructing texts that are intended to "write the world" with mathematics: How mathematically precise and explicit should this writing be? Must the student "teach" mathematics to the audience, or only present results of their mathematical investigation? What writing strategies manage to unify mathematical and political or moral positions? What kinds of writing prompts will encourage particular kinds of social justice mathematics writing?

We hope to point out varied strategies for writing that bridge mathematical insights and social, political or moral perspectives, and to notice different ways of valuing this kind of mathematical writing (Barwell, 2018). This conversation may heighten awareness of the complexity of social justice mathematics writing and the pressing need for wider pedagogical guidance towards it.

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